

The comparative study of efficacy and complications of inguinal hernia block vs spinal anaesthesia in inguinal hernia repair.

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Abstract

Background: Postoperative pain is an adverse outcome that distresses the patient, prolongs the hospital stay.

Aim: To compare the efficacy of Inguinal hernia block and spinal anaesthesia for inguinal hernia repair.

Methodology: This is a randomized controlled study done in 60 patients scheduled for elective inguinal hernia repair with Group A (n = 30) Inguinal hernia block and Group B (n = 30) were given Spinal Anaesthesia. time of onset, duration of analgesia , hemodynamic parameters and associated complications were studied.

Patients in age group 20 to 60 years with ASA 1, 2 & with primary uncomplicated or with unilateral hernia were included.

Results: The onset of analgesia was 4.27 ± 1.437 in group A (spinal group) and 14.87 ± 6.152 minutes in group B (inguinal block group) . The mean duration of analgesia was 235.47 ± 71.619 and 346.97 ± 124.506 minutes in group A and B respectively . In our present study, in group A, 1 patient (3.3%) felt mild pain, and 1 patient (3.3%) felt moderate pain. However, in group B, 6 patients (20.0%) felt mild pain, and 20 patients (66.7%) felt moderate pain. A significant decrease in MAP blood pressure , systolic blood pressure, and diastolic blood pressure was observed in spinal anaesthesia group . There was no significant decrease in heart rate in our present study .

Conclusion: The onset of analgesia is quicker in spinal anaesthesia group but prolonged with inguinal field block. Inguinal hernia block is associated with better intraoperative hemodynamic stability and fewer postoperative complications.

Keywords: *Inguinal hernia block, spinal anaesthesia, hemodynamic stability, postoperative pain.*

Introduction

Pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage. Postoperative pain is an adverse outcome that distresses the patient, prolongs the hospital stay and increases the incidence of admission after surgery. The hernia is defined by Sir Astley Cooper (1804) as “protrusion of any viscus or part of the viscus through an abnormal opening in the walls of its containing cavity.”[1]

Inguinal hernia repair is one of the most frequent procedure performed. General, spinal, epidural, local anaesthetic techniques can be used, each having its advantages and disadvantages.

General anaesthesia carries risks of possible airway complications, post-operative deterioration of cognitive function, sore throat, nausea, vomiting and a prolonged period of immobilization with an associated risk of deep vein thrombosis and more extended hospital stay.

Spinal or continuous epidural anaesthesia allows the surgeon greater freedom to manoeuvre within the operative field since the anaesthetized region is more significant than local anaesthesia. However, these modes of anaesthesia carry their infrequent risks such as urinary retention, prolonged anaesthetic effect, spinal headache. [2]

The aim of postoperative pain relief is to provide subjective comfort in addition to inhibition trauma induced nociceptive impulses to blunt autonomic and somatic reflex response to pain and subsequently enhance restoration of function by allowing patient to breath, cough and ambulatory more easily, preventing postoperative pulmonary complications and inhibiting sympathetic nervous system stimulation, resulting in earlier discharge from the hospital and minimizing the total hospital expenditure. Peripheral nerve block is now well accepted component of comprehensive anaesthesia care.

Inguinal hernia repair is one of the most frequent procedure performed. Local anaesthesia with appropriate analgesia appears to be safe for most of the unilateral open inguinal hernia repair with less post anaesthetic side effects although spinal anaesthesia is more commonly performed .So, we planned a comparative study for inguinal hernia repair under spinal anaesthesia and local anaesthesia with inguinal field block.

Aim and objectives

The present study was conducted with the following aim and objectives-

1. To compare the effects of spinal anaesthesia and inguinal field block for inguinal hernia repair.
2. To study the onset of analgesia , duration of analgesia and quality of analgesia during the intraoperative and postoperative period in the two groups.
3. To analyze the effects of anaesthesia technique on hemodynamic parameters.
4. To study the side effects associated with the two techniques.

Materials and Methods

This present study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology of tertiary care teaching institute in western Maharastra.

STUDY PERIOD : 6 months

A total of 60 patients undergoing elective unilateral open inguinal hernia repair were included in the study after obtaining informed written consent and ethical committee approval.

STUDY DESIGN : The present study was conducted as a Randomized controlled study. Sixty patients with ASA grade I & II & III presenting for elective open inguinal hernia repair were randomly assigned to two groups (30 each) . Only patients meeting the selection criteria were included in the study.

Sample Technique : Simple Random sampling was used.

Group A (n= 30) : Patients were given inguinal field block , **Group-B (n = 30) :** Patients were given spinal anaesthesia.

INCLUSION CRITERIA :

- 1) Patients in the age group of 20-60 years
- 2) ASA category I and II and III posted for elective inguinal hernia repair
- 3) Patients with a primary uncomplicated hernia
- 4) Patients with a unilateral hernia
- 5) No known history of allergy, sensitivity or other forms of reaction to local anaesthetic drugs

EXCLUSION CRITERIA :

1. Obesity
2. Patients with psychiatric problems
3. Patients with complicated hernias like irreducibility, obstruction, gangrene.
4. Known case of history of allergy, sensitivity or other forms of reaction to local anaesthetic drugs.

The thorough pre-anaesthetic evaluation was done a day before the elective surgery.

A thorough physical examination , systemic examination and airway assessment was done .

Height , weight and vital signs of the patient were recorded .

The following investigations were carried out in all the patients : Complete blood count, bleeding time, clotting time, blood urea, serum creatinine, random blood sugar, ECG. On the day of surgery, an intravenous line was secured with 18 G cannula.

Standard monitors such as NIBP, ECG, Pulse oximeter monitors were connected, and baseline pulse rate, blood pressure, ECG, respiratory rate and SpO₂ were recorded.

Group A received inguinal block technique .

Group B received Spinal anaesthesia in sitting or lateral position with 25 gauge Quincke spinal needle in L3-L4 intervertebral space with 3 ml of 0.5% bupivacaine .

PARAMETERS STUDIED : The following parameters were studied

1. Time of onset of block and duration of block
2. Pulse rate(PR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), Mean arterial pressure (MAP), Oxygen saturation (SPO2) were monitored intraoperatively and postoperatively.
3. Quality of analgesia using Visual Analog score (VAS score)

Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis has been carried out in the present study.

Results on continuous measurements are presented on Mean ± SD (Min-Max)

P value less than 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

The Statistical analysis was performed with Open Epi, Version 3 open source calculator and Microsoft word and Excel have been used to generate graphs, tables etc.

Results and Discussion

A total of 60 patients undergoing hernia surgery were randomly allocated into two groups as follows:

Group A : Patients received inguinal field block.

Group B : Patients received spinal anaesthesia.

The mean age of the patients in group A was 42.63 ± 10.519 years while in group B was 47.07 ± 10.636. The results was not statistically significant (p=0.343) .

Table 1: Onset of Block

Onset of Block (in mts)	Group					
	Group A		Group B		Total	
	No. Of Patients	%	No. Of Patients	%	No. Of Patients	%
2-3	8	26.7	2	6.7	10	16.7
4-5	21	70.0	1	3.3	22	36.7
Above 6	1	3.3	27	90.0	28	46.7
Total	30	100.0	30	100.0	60	100.0
Mean block	4.27±1.437		14.87±6.152		9.57±6.941	
Chi-square	x ² Value = 45.925 dt =2, p=0.000 (Highly significant) (P<0.001)					

The mean onset of block in Group A was 4.27 ± 1.437 minutes where as in Group B was 14.87± 6.152 minutes which was statistically significant (p<0.001).

Table 2: Duration of Block

	Group A (n=30) Mean±SD	Group B (n=30) Mean±SD	Mean Difference	P- value	Significant
Duration of analgesia (in min)	235.47 ± 71.619	346.97 ± 124.506	-111.50	0.000**	Significant

The mean duration of analgesia was 235.47±71.619 minutes in group A whereas in group B , the mean duration of analgesia was 346.97±124.506 minutes which was statistically significant (p=0.000).

Graph 1: VAS Score

Out Of 30 patients in group A, 28 patients complained of no pain, 1 patient had mild pain and 1 patient had moderate pain whereas in group B, 7 patients had no pain, 9 patients had mild pain, 10 patients had moderate pain, 4 patients had severe pain which was statistically highly significant ($p=0.000$).

Graph 2: Heart Rate

HEMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS :

In Group A, the mean heart rate was 82.40 ± 14.369 per minute which was increased to 84.00 ± 19.412 at 15 minutes. In Group B, the mean heart rate was 79.30 ± 10.083 per minute which was decreased to 77.23 ± 11.116 minutes at 15 minutes. However, there was no statistically significant difference in the heart rate difference between the two groups at any time interval ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3: Difference in MAP

Time Interval (min)	Group A (n=30) Mean±SD	Group B (n=30) Mean±SD	Mean Difference	P-value	Sig.
Baseline	91.74±9.436	94.55±6.054	-2.81	0.214	Not Significant
0 Min	93.78±8.342	94.60±6.062	-0.82	0.696	Not Significant
5 Min	86.73±6.777	92.32±6.457	-5.59	0.007	Significant
15 Min	86.33±6.738	92.80±6.150	-6.47	0.000	Significant
30 Min	88.38±7.187	93.44±6.447	-5.06	0.003	Significant
60 Min	89.41±7.308	95.65±7.604	-6.24	0.001	Significant
90 Min	90.64±7.472	97.56±8.101	-6.92	0.002	Significant

Table 3: Shows the comparison of mean arterial pressure at 0,5,15,30,60,90 minutes among the group A and group B. The difference between the mean arterial pressure between the two groups were statistically significant.

Table 4: Demographic features and VAS among the two groups.

	Group A (IB)	Group B (SA)	P value
Age	48.85±15.5	50.87±11.7	0.13
Gender	M 100%	M 100%	
ASA I / II	19/12	22/9	
VAS 0	21.26±11.9	10.26±7.4	0.011
VAS 30	15.48±5.05	10.32±1.8	<0.001
VAS at 2 hrs			
R	24.19±7	26.1±9.55	0.09
M	32.26±11.75	37.74±9.9	0.42
VAS at 4 hrs			
R	32.58±7.5	37.1±7.39	0.9
M	46.45±4.18	42.9±8.4	0.29
VAS at 12 hrs			
R	38.39±7.35	47.77±7.91	0.77
M	48.71±7.63	54.19±7.2	0.8

Rescue Analgesia (hours)	4.5	3.9	
Total Analgesic Consumption	3.2±0.2	2.8±0.2	0.9
Duration of surgery in min	56.7±13.5	59.16±10.23	0.13
Interval to pain free ambulation	1.8±0.25	3.6±0.5	<0.001

Table-5: Post-operative complications among two groups

Complications	Group	
	Group A (n=30)	Group B (n=30)
	No. of Patients	No. of Patients
Nausea	1 (3.3)	2 (6.6)
Seroma	7 (23.3)	5 (16.7)
Vomiting	2 (6.7)	1 (3.3)
Headache	5 (16.7)	0 (0.0)
Hypertension	8 (26.7)	0 (0.0)
Urinary Retention	13 (43.3)	1 (3.3)
Testicular Pain	2 (6.7)	0 (0.0)
Wound Infection	2 (6.7)	4 (13.3)
Wound Hematoma	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)

COMPLICATIONS :

Complications like nausea, vomiting, headache, hypotension, urinary retention, testicular pain were more in group A whereas local complications like wound infections were more in group B

Table-6: Post-operative complications among two groups

	Group A	Group B	P-value
PONV	2 (8%)	5 (20%)	0.43
Hypotension	0	4 (12.9%)	
Arrhythmias	0	0	
Urinary Retention	0	3 (9.7%)	
Headache	0	3 (9.7%)	
Hematoma	1 (3%)	0	
Scrotal swelling	2 (6%)	0	

Discussion

Inguinal hernia repair, which is the commonest surgery, has been performed under general, spinal, epidural, and local anaesthesia techniques. According to recent European Hernia society guidelines,

In an open hernia repair, the local anaesthetic should be considered for all adult primary reducible unilateral inguinal hernia. [3] There is a level of inertia in adopting this technique among anaesthesiologists. Initially, the surgeon used to give local anaesthesia at the operation site but this did not provide complete anaesthesia. Ilioinguinal and iliohypogastric nerve block provides somatic block over the lower abdomen, and visceral pain is often relieved by giving supplemental local anaesthetic at the time of sac dissection. This study evaluated the efficacy, safety, feasibility, advantages, and complications of ilioinguinal and iliohypogastric nerve block by a single puncture technique combined with wound infiltration through the same puncture compared to spinal anaesthesia. We chose the modification of Dalen's technique used in children. It was described by P Carre et al., [4] The advantage of using a single puncture technique is less discomfort to the patient by avoiding multiple punctures as described in classical technique. Multiple puncture techniques of inguinal field block were associated with transient femoral nerve palsy causing weakness

of knee extensors, cord hematoma, thrombosis of the dorsal vein of the penis, wound hematoma, and wound infection.

The present study is a hospital-based randomized clinical study in 60 patients scheduled to undergo elective hernia repair. In the present study, the mean age was 42.63 ± 10.519 in group A and 47.07 ± 10.638 in group B and all the patients were males. Age and sex incidence of patients in our study were similar to other studies. [5 , 6]

The time of onset of analgesia was taken from completion of the study drugs injection until the patient did not feel pinprick at the incision site. The present study compared ilioinguinal, iliohypogastric nerve block with spinal anaesthesia for inguinal hernia repair for the onset of analgesia and found 4.27 ± 1.437 minutes in group A (spinal group) and 14.87 ± 6.152 minutes in group B (inguinal block group) (p -value < 0.001). Our study results are inconsistent with Pramod et al. [7] and Khedkar et al. [8] , The results of our study are inconsistent with chatrapati et al., [9] in a spinal group. Still, in the ilioinguinal and iliohypogastric nerve block group, our study results are not inconsistent with chatrapati et al., the reason being in our study, we used Bupivacaine alone. In contrast, Chatrapati et al., used bupivacaine 0.5% + 2% lignocaine with adrenaline. So the onset of analgesia was faster in Chatrapati et al. than in our study. Our study's result is not consistent with Fekrey et al., [10] in a spinal group because we used Bupivacaine alone. In contrast, Fekrey et al., used 0.5% bupivacaine + 25 microgram fentanyl as an adjuvant. So the onset of analgesia was faster in study done by Fekrey et al.,

Pain is the most common concerning factor for the patient undergoing surgery. Although pain is typically regarded as a primary indicator of tissue damage, it does not always correlate with an identifiable causative injury. The perception of pain is supported by sensory neurons (nociceptors) and neural afferent pathways. Both spinal and local anaesthesia involves limited body areas and does not interfere with other organs and ventilation. Spinal anaesthesia can produce complete sensory and motor blockade. The local anaesthetic technique's success, consisting of a blockade of the ilioinguinal and iliohypogastric nerves, depends on a thorough understanding of nerves' anatomy. In our present study, in group A, 1 patient (3.3%) felt mild pain, and 1 patient (3.3%) felt moderate pain. However, in group B, 6 patients (20.0%) felt mild pain, and 20 patients (66.7%) felt moderate pain. The difference is statistically significant ($p=0.00$). The results of our study were comparable to other studies. [7,8,9,10]

The present study compared ilioinguinal and iliohypogastric nerve block with spinal anaesthesia for inguinal hernia repair and found a statistically significant decrease in mean arterial pressure, systolic blood pressure, and diastolic blood pressure of spinal anaesthesia as compared to preoperative values in the first 30 minutes. There was a statistically significant difference in mean arterial blood pressure, systolic blood pressure, and diastolic blood pressure between both groups. The study conducted by Nehme et al., [11] found that hypotension incidence was highest in spinal anaesthesia cases (19 %). Our results are consistent with other studies. The significant decrease is due to the sympathetic blockade caused by spinal anaesthesia, leading to vasodilation, Peripheral venous pooling, and decreased cardiac output. The intraoperative fluid requirement was higher in spinal anaesthesia to expand the intravascular compartment and maintain good intravascular volume and blood pressure. Therefore, ilioinguinal and iliohypogastric nerve block can be a choice technique in patients with low ejection fraction.

There was no significant decrease in heart rate in our present study, and none of the patients in either group, especially group B, where spinal anaesthesia was given developed bradycardia.

It is observed that local anaesthesia for inguinal hernia repair causes a minimal physiological disturbance. This may be particularly useful for patients with cardiovascular and respiratory diseases and geriatric patients with compromised cardiorespiratory reserve.

The inguinal hernia repair is a common surgery with almost no mortality. The emphasis is on low recurrence rates and other complications like nausea and vomiting, urinary retention, hypotension, wound hematoma, wound sepsis, testicular

pain/swelling, headache, and respiratory complications. The choice of anaesthesia depends on low complication rates.

Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) still is the most troublesome adverse event encountered in the recovery room, despite advances in prevention and treatment. The present study compared ilioinguinal, iliohypogastric nerve block with spinal anaesthesia for inguinal hernia repair, and found a 6.7 % incidence in the spinal anaesthesia group. In contrast, its incidence was 3.3 % of the local anaesthesia group. Our results are consistent with Parmod Kumar et al., [7] Chatrapati et al., [9] Anurag Jain et al., [12] Natasha et al., [13] S. Sesaiah et al., [14] in the spinal anaesthesia group and are consistent with Anurag Jain et al., Natasha et al., S.Sesaiah et al., in the local anaesthesia group.

Postoperative urinary retention is common after anaesthesia and surgery. The incidence of postoperative urinary retention is also affected by the anaesthesia technique. Urinary retention is thought to be secondary to the prolonged block of bladder autonomic innervations. It may also be related to the age of the patient and the volume of the fluid received. In the present study, 1 patient (3.3%) complained of urinary retention in the local anaesthesia group, whereas 13 patients (43.3%) complained of urinary retention in the spinal anaesthesia group.

Our present study showed a 26 % incidence of hypotension whereas 0% incidence in the local anaesthesia group. The difference was statistically significant.. The results of the present study was comparable to Chatrapati et al., [9]

In the present study, wound sepsis was present in 2 patients (6.7%) in group A (spinal anaesthesia) and 4 patients (13.3%) in group B (local anaesthesia). The study conducted by Pradeep Goel et al., [6] found that wound infection was present in 1 patient (4%) of group A (Local anaesthesia) and 3 patients (12%) patients of group B (spinal anaesthesia).

In the present study, 5 patients (16.7%) complained of headaches, whereas in group B (local anaesthesia group), none complained of headaches. Headache was probably due to dural puncture in the spinal anaesthesia group.

Inguinal hernia repair, which is the commonest surgery, has been performed under general, spinal, epidural, and local anaesthesia techniques. According to recent European Hernia society guidelines,

LIMITATIONS : Since the study did not include the pediatric population, so could not access opinions regarding local anaesthesia's feasibility in this age group.

Conclusion

The conclusion of our study is as that -

Field block provides prolonged postoperative analgesia, although the onset of anesthesia is earlier in spinal anaesthesia. Thus our study concluded that local anaesthesia is superior to spinal anaesthesia for postoperative analgesia.

Field block is associated with better intraoperative hemodynamic stability and fewer postoperative complications.

Field block can be an alternative technique for patients with complex medical conditions who are unsuitable for spinal and general anaesthesia.

References.

- 1) Flangan L, Bascom JU. Repair of the groin hernia outpatient approach with local anesthesia. *Surg Clin North Am* 1984;64(2):257-267.
- 2) Iles T. The management of elective hernia repair. *Ann Plast Surg* 1979;2:538-542
- 3) Dongare DH, Dongare HC. Comparison of ilioinguinal iliohypogastric nerve block versus spinal anaesthesia for hernia repair as daycare surgery. *Perspectives in medical research*. 2014; 2: 7-12.
- 4) Caree P, Mollet J, Le Poutel S, Costey G, Ecoffey C *Ann Fr Anesth Reanim*. Ilio-inguinal Ilio – hypogastric nerve block with a single puncture: an alternative for anaesthesia in emergency inguinal surgery. 2001;20:643-6.
- 5) Yang B, Liang MJ, Zhang YC. Use of local or epidural anesthesia inguinal hernia repair: a randomized trial. *Zhonghua Wai Ke Za Zhi* 2008.
- 6) Pradeep Goyal, Shiv Kumar Sharma, Kamaljeet Singh Jaswal , Sandeep Goyal, Mushtaq Ahmed, Gauravrai Sharma, Poonam Pandotra. Comparison of inguinal hernia repair under local anaesthesia versus spinal anaesthesia. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*, Volume 13,

Issue 1:54-59.

- 7) Parmod Kumar, Tripat KB, Ashwani Kumar, Uma S. Comparison of IlioInguinal Ilio-hypogastric nerve block with spinal anaesthesia for inguinal hernia repair. *International Journal of Medical and Health Research*. 2019; 5(4) : 37-42.
- 8) Khedkar SM, Bhalerao PM, Yemul –Golhar SR, Kelkar KV. Ultrasoundguided ilioinguinal and iliohypogastric nerve block, a comparison with the conventional technique. An observational study. *Saudi J Anaesth* .2015;293-7.
- 9) Chatrapati S, Sahu A, Patil S. Comparative Evaluation of Ilioinguinal / Iliohypogastric Nerve Block with Spinal Anaesthesia for Unilateral Open Inguinal Hernia Repair. *International Journal of Contemporary Medical Research*, 2016;3:1177 -81.
- 10) Fekrey DM, Megahed NA, EL-Lakany MH, Yakout MM. Ultrasoundguided ilioinguinal, iliohypogastric, and genitofemoral nerve block versus spinal subarachnoid blockade for inguinal hernia repair. *Res Opin Anesth Intensive Care*. 2017;4: 29-34
- 11) Nehme AE. Groin hernias in elderly patients. Management and prognosis. *Am J Surg*. 1983;146:257-60.
- 12) Anurag Jain, Rajiv Jain, Ashish Choudhrie. Local Anaesthesia Versus Spinal Anaesthesia in Inguinal Hernia Surgery. An Evidence-Based Approach. *International Journal of Anatomy, Radiology and Surgery* .2019 Jul, Vol -8(3): S001-S004.
- 13) Natasha Shafique et al., Comparison of Efficacy of Spinal Anaesthesia And Sub –Fascial Local Anaesthetic Inguinal field Block for Open Inguinal Hernia Repair – A Single Institutional Experience. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad* 2015;27(1):197-200.
- 14) S.Seshaiah, S.Sreenivasa Rao, Khader Faheem, Hareesh GSR, Haribabu M.A. A Comparative Study of Hernioplasty for Uncomplicated Inguinal Hernia Done Under Local Anaesthesia Versus Spinal Anaesthesia. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*. 2019 ;18(5) :24-31.